

An overlooked dicopper(I) helicate

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It is pointed out that $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{L})_2(\text{LH})_2]$ where $\text{LH} \equiv \text{Ph}-\text{N}=\text{N}-\text{C}(\text{Me})=\text{N}-\text{OH}$, is the first structurally characterised [M. H. Dickman and R. J. Doedens, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1980, 19, 3112] double stranded helicate where metal coordination and H-bonding work in tandem to bring about a helical topology:

We are engaged in studying helicates for the last few years^{1,2} in connection with understanding some of the self processes operative in nature. The term "helicate" was introduced by Lehn in 1987 for describing di- or poly-nuclear metal complexes having helical topologies³. Since then has been realised the significance of a synthetic helical molecule. During our work, we have come across the X-ray crystal structure of a dinuclear copper(I) complex reported by Dickman and Doedens⁴ in 1980. Herein we point out that this complex is one of the few helicates structurally characterised before 1987. It is noted that this complex, has gone largely unnoticed in the area of helicates i.e. not cited even in any of the most extensive reviews⁵⁻⁷ on helicates only because Dickman and Doedens have not explicitly categorised it as a helical metal complex.

The copper (I) complex under discussion, (1), was origi-

nally synthesised by Gupta *et al.*⁸. The structural motif (A), recognised early in the crystal structure of bis(dimethylglyoximate)nickel(II)⁹, is quite common in the chemistry of oximes^{10,11}. This motif operates in an intramolecular fashion. This mode of H-bonding is not possible in (1) because of the type of disposition of the oxime and oximate O atoms brought about by the tetrahedral geometry of the metal. However, the motif (B) can lead to intermolecular interaction. This very mode of H-bonding makes (1) a "Janus"

molecule¹² having two recognition sites, each of which is monodentate. Two units of (1) interact in a self-complementary manner to generate the supramolecular entity (1₂). A view of its X-ray crystal structure is given in (Fig. 1) showing the helical topology explicitly. It is the torsion angle N-O-O-N (it should be noted that the O--H--O moieties are absolutely linear) of 93.8° which is responsible for the

Fig. 1. A view of the helical topology of (1₂). Colour code of the discs : red, Cu; green, N; yellow, O; white, C. The H atoms are omitted for clarity.

helicity in (1₂). The observed H-bonding is very strong being one of the shortest known H-bonds^{4,13} and persists in solution⁸ also.

It is now well understood that helices are formed by themselves¹⁴. Helical topologies in biological and organic molecules are facilitated by various factors. One of them is H-

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bonding^{12,14-16}, as found in DNA. However, examples of helical inorganic molecules where H-bonding plays a dominant role in determining the topology have been available much after 1987¹⁷. In this regard, (**1**₂) is possibly the first structurally characterised metal complex where metal coordination and H-bonding work in tandem to result in helicity.

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